

UUU	UCU	UAU	UGU
UUC	UCC	UAC	UGC
UUA	UCA	UAA	UGA
UUG	UCG	UAG	UGG
CUU	CCU	CAU	CGU
CUC	CCC	CAC	CGC
CUA	CCA	CAA	CGA
CUG	CCG	CAG	CGG
AUU	ACU	AAU	AGU
AUC	ACC	AAC	AGC
AUA	ACA	AAA	AGA
AUG	ACG	AAG	AGG
GUU	GCU	GAU	GGU
GUC	GCC	GAC	GGC
GUA	GCA	GAA	GGA
GUG	GCG	GAG	GGG